

A significant study on the current scenario of internet marketing among MSME (Micro Small and Medium Enterprises) sector in the Indian context

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Abstract:

In terms of its contribution to the socioeconomic development of our nation in terms of GDP growth, employment, and export, the MSME sector of India is regarded as the backbone of our economy. However, there has always been a worry that Indian MSMEs haven't truly reached their full potential for company expansion because of issues with exposure, awareness, intelligence, and other aspects of promoting their goods and services. The objective of this study is to ascertain the importance of internet marketing for micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in augmenting their business operations, which is currently imperative. Additionally, this research aims to comprehend the constraints faced by the MSME sector in India regarding the adoption of internet marketing as their primary mode of operation. This will be achieved by conducting a comprehensive analysis of published research and literature to evaluate the current situation and provide suitable recommendations to encourage collaboration between MSMEs and policy makers. The Micro Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) sector plays a noteworthy role in the advancement of the country's socioeconomic status. The sector has acquired significant importance owing to its contribution to India's GDP and exports. The industry has made noteworthy contributions towards the advancement of entrepreneurship, specifically in the semi-urban and rural regions of India.

Keywords: Socioeconomic development, internet marketing, entrepreneurship, exposure, awareness

Introduction:

MSMEs in India plays an indispensable role in the economic development of the nation through contribution to the manufacturing output, increasing foreign exchange earnings, provision of employment opportunities, exports, and promoting balanced economic development (Mohan & Ali, 2018). India has about 36 million MSMEs providing about 80 million employment opportunities, contributing to about 8% of the gross domestic product (GDP) and about 33% of total manufacturing output (Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, 2018). Indian MSMEs are witnessing an extremely dynamic and multi-faceted business scenario (Jena & Thatte, 2018). The increasingly complex cost structures and an insistent quest of delivering high customer satisfaction are necessitating the adoption of ICT (Information Communication Technology) tools including the adoption of internet marketing and e-commerce to sustain in the present scenario where competition is increasingly becoming global, especially due to the influx of imports from neighboring China. Though there have been studies on usage and challenges in adoption of ICTs amongst MSMEs in different economic contexts (Giotopoulos et al., 2017; Gono et al., 2008; Osorio-Gallego et al., 2016; Perez-Soltero et al., 2017; Suhartanto & Leo, 2018), challenges faced by Indian MSMEs on adoption of ICTs especially internet marketing and e-commerce has not received enough attention in the literature.

This study tried to address this gap by conducting primary research among owners of Indian MSMEs, firstly by conducting semi-structured interviews amongst a dozen MSME owners and that was later followed up by a survey amongst over a hundred MSME owners. The study investigated the opportunities, challenges and barriers faced by MSMEs in India over the adoption of internet marketing and e-commerce channels.

MSME's as an Indian Perspective:

In terms of the size and structure of the units, the range of goods and services, the volume of production, and the use of technology, Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises in India offer a heterogeneous and diversified type of fabric. As auxiliary units, these businesses are a great addition to the large-scale industry. They make a major contribution to the nation's socioeconomic development. In India, MSMEs account for over 80% of all industries and create about 8,000 value-added goods. A variety of viewpoints are provided by a good definition of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) and their suitable classification in a national or international context. In the private sector, small industrial or company units are typically referred to as "MSME"s. MSMEs have been categorized differently in various settings depending on their type of assets and scale of production, while others have characterized those units based on the number of jobs they create, shareholder funding they get, the size of their

investments, or the amount of goods they sell, etc. The World Bank defines a business as an MSMEs when it satisfies two out of the three requirements, i.e., employee strength, asset size, or annual sales. The Government of India (GOI) passed the Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises Development (MSMED) Act in 2006, providing a legal foundation and framework for these business owners by uniformly categorizing and classifying them. The foregoing restrictions do not include the cost of land, buildings, or other specifically mentioned items. This division includes both manufacturing and service sector industries. Over the years, the MSME sector in our nation has experienced constant and noteworthy growth and development.

Market Size:

More than 60 SMEs are anticipated to enter the market in one year (2021–2022) to raise equity money to suit their company needs, according to the BSE SME (small and medium enterprises) platform. 16 SMEs entered the market through the initial public offering (IPO) method, raising Rs. 100 crore (US\$ 13.74 million) in 2020. The Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) announced in June 2021 that it has partnered with the Electronics and Computer Software Export Promotion Council (ESC) to raise awareness of the benefits of listing among small

firms and start-ups. MSMEs are urged to sell their goods online, particularly through the Government e-Marketplace (GeM), which is owned and operated by the government and where Ministries and PSUs (public sector undertakings) source their supplies. By the end of November 2022, the GeM portal had processed 12.28 million orders totaling Rs. 334,933 crores (\$40.97 billion) for 62,247 buyer organisations from 5.44 million registered sellers and service providers. The Udyam Registration platform registered 14,392,652 MSMEs as of February 22nd, 2023, according to data from the Ministry of Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises, replacing the previous procedure of submitting an Udyog Aadhaar Memorandum (UAM). 13,834,411 micro-enterprises were registered, making up 96.12% of all businesses, followed by 446,980 small businesses and 40,400 medium-sized businesses. To ensure that sufficient liquidity is maintained in business operations, domestic business needs a significant financial stimulus from the government and financial institutions in the form of favourable working capital loans. With 72% of payments made digitally compared to 28% of cash transactions, Indian Micro, Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (MSMEs) are quickly moving away from cash transactions. Increased digital use offers opportunities for the industry to continue growing.

Above image showing registered MSME’s in India in FY22 (Lakh Units)

Statutory bodies:

MSME Ministry has four statutory bodies namely, Khadi and Village Industries Commission (KVIC) who is responsible for promoting and developing Khadi and village industries for providing employment opportunities in rural areas, thereby strengthening the rural economy, Coir Board in charge of promoting overall development of the coir industry and improving living conditions of workers in this industry, National Small Industries Corporation Limited (NSIC) responsible for promoting, aiding and fostering growth of micro and small enterprises in the country, generally on commercial basis, National Institute for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, (NI-MSME) in-charge of enterprise promotion and entrepreneurship development, enabling enterprise creation,

performing diagnostic development studies for policy formulation, etc. and lastly, Mahatma Gandhi Institute for Rural Industrialization (MGIRI) responsible for accelerating rural industrialization for sustainable village economy, attract professionals and experts to Gram Swaraj, empower traditional artisans, encourage innovation through pilot study/field trials and R&D for alternative technology using local resources. Through November 2020, the new online MSME/Udyam Registration system launched by the Union MSME Ministry has successfully registered over 1.1 million MSMEs since its launch on July 1, 2020. The Ministry of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises has extended the expiration date of the Udyog Aadhaar Memorandum to June 30, 2022.

Government Policies:

For the development of MSMEs in the nation, the Indian government has created a number of policies:

1. The government updated its MSMEs loan guarantee programme in February 2023, and it will go into effect on April 1st with the entry of Rs 9,000 crore (\$1.09 billion) into the corpus. This plan would permit an additional Rs 2 lakh crore (\$24.41 billion) in collateral-free guaranteed loans while also lowering the cost of the credit by around 1%.
2. A single Skill India Digital Platform will be developed, the government declared in its budget for 2023–2024, in order to facilitate demand-based formal skilling, link with employers—including MSMEs—and make access to entrepreneurship programmes easier.
3. As of July 8, 2022, 10.03 million loans had been approved under the Pradhan Mantri MUDRA Yojana (PMMY) scheme, and 73,199.89 crore (US\$ 9.15 billion) had been disbursed.
4. MSMEs were given an Emergency Credit Line Guarantee Scheme (ECLGS) budget of Rs. 50,000 crore (US\$ 6.55 billion) in the Union Budget for 2022–2023
5. Raising and Accelerating MSME Performance (RAMP) was given a budget of Rs. 6,062.45 crore (US\$ 808 million) on March 30, 2022 by the Indian government. The plan intends to increase market and credit access, promote center-state links and cooperation, address issues with late payments, and green MSMEs. It also aims to develop institutions and governance at the centre and state levels.
6. The Indian government introduced the Special Credit Linked Capital Subsidy Scheme (SCLCSS) for the services industry in November 2021. This programme will assist businesses in the services industry in meeting various technological criteria.
7. The Ministry of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises introduced SAMBHAV in November 2021 as a nationwide awareness campaign to encourage local manufacturing and entrepreneurship and drive economic growth.
3. The national government unveiled a brand-new programme in June 2022 dubbed "Promotion of MSMEs in North Eastern Region and Sikkim." By constructing mini-technological centres, growing both new and existing industrial estates, and marketing tourism, this project's primary goal was to promote MSMEs in the North East.
4. In November 2021, the Small Industries Development Bank of India (SIDBI) and Google signed an agreement to test social impact financing, providing microbusinesses with financial support up to Rs. 1 crore (US\$ 133,939.60) at discounted interest rates. Google India Pvt. Ltd. GIPL would provide a corpus of US\$ 15 million (about Rs. 110 crore) for micro firms as a crisis reaction to COVID-19 in order to revitalize the Indian MSME sector.
5. Predictive analytics-based shipment tracking was introduced by online freight forwarder Freightwalla in November 2021 for MSME exporters and importers to help companies reduce the risk of shipment delays and boost supply chain effectiveness.
6. Supply chain financing (SCF) platform Cash invoice stated in November 2021 that it will provide MSMEs with over Rs. 10,000 crore (US\$ 1.33 billion) in financing in the coming year thanks to a US\$ 1 million Pre-Series A fundraising round from Accion Venture Lab.
7. MSMEs received marketing support in October 2021 from Sundaram Finance and the MSME Development Institute (Chennai).
8. Through an incubator programme, which will provide innovators with possibilities to create and foster ideas for the manufacture of new products, MSMEs' entrepreneurial and managerial development will be accomplished.
9. Boeing awarded a contract to the MSME Aerospace Engineers Private Limited of Tamil Nadu in September 2021 to manufacture and deliver essential aircraft components.

Recent Evolutions:

Significant recent changes in MSMEs include:

1. The government indicated in its budget for 2023–2024 that Entity DigiLocker will be set up for MSMEs, major corporations, and charitable trusts to use in order to securely store and share documents online.
2. The government declared in February 2023 that in cases where MSMEs failed to fulfill contracts within the Covid period, 95% of the forfeited cash due to bid or performance security will be reimbursed to MSMEs by the government and government undertakings.

Potential for growth opportunities in MSME Sector:

Micro, Small, and Medium-Sized Enterprises have made some contributions to the nation's economic growth. In terms of creating jobs, the MSME sector in India comes in second place only to agriculture. About 95% of the industrial units, 45% of manufacturing output, and 40% of all exports from the nation come from this sector. MSMEs have more potential to expand as supporting businesses that encourage broader industrial expansion. MSMEs have greater access to raw materials, subsidies, and other incentives under cluster programmes since they are less capital intensive and more employment-friendly. By utilizing the available resources, the nation has a

significant growth potential to establish and improve the capacity of businesses in the manufacturing and service sectors. The MSMEs have a tonne of room to expand as supporting industries, which will fuel even more industrial growth. Increased infrastructure spending, an abundance of job possibilities, the emergence of a strong private sector with both small and large businesses/corporate houses, and a surge in consumerism are all possible drivers of growth. If an environment-friendly regulatory framework and conducive infrastructure support are made available for its functional operations, the MSME sector has the potential to become the foundation of the Indian economy and to continue as an engine of growth. In order to address new challenges and ensure their sustainability, this sector has been performing noticeably better than the overall rate of GDP (average 8% growth per year) and the overall industrial output (measured by the Index of Industrial Production, or IIP). A target of increasing their share of contribution from the current 8% to 20% by 2022 should be included in the roadmap for MSME development, as well as targets for a significant increase in the creation of employment opportunities up to 50%, an improvement in MSME contribution in the key public and private industry sector by meeting the rising domestic demand, indigenization and significant substitution, and growth in foreign exports. The current "Make in India" effort by the Indian government will have a significant impact on indigenization and will also draw a big amount of international investment. Similar to this, the "Digital India" programme provides MSMEs with enormous opportunity to actively engage in the information and communication technology (ICT) industry.

Major suggestions to MSME are in current context:

The following suggestions will help MSMEs use internet marketing effectively and successfully accept it: Many small business owners base their company's success solely on their network of connections and relationships, relying on traditional marketing strategies like word-of-mouth advertising and personal recommendations to attract new clients. When your customers are spending more and more time online, it is perilous to think of any business from the greatest corporation to the lone proprietor, or anything in between as exclusively offline. Even for firms that may perceive themselves to be largely or conventionally offline, using the web as a business tool is crucial. Despite the fact that their personal selling slogan or capacity may make business seem to exist, the web can play a significant role in that. Therefore, regardless of how well-established your enterprises are offline, it's essential to set up the fundamentals

of your online presence now that things are changing and we're transitioning to our new normal lives and business practices. There are several easy measures you can take to start enjoying the benefits that the internet may bring, even if you run a small business and don't have a lot of money, employees, or spare time to engage in complex web strategies and implementations.

Besides the above suggestions some of the other major suggestions can be as follows:

1. Make Your Business Information Accessible Online:

Making your company as accessible as possible and allowing customers to find you whenever they want is the key to maximizing the potential of the internet. Your clients may find your goods or services online, and as a result, they contact companies and organizations that are simple to find online to inquire about their needs. Obviously, this does not imply that the company should be present on every single online platform; rather, it calls for careful consideration when deciding which platforms are most significant to your target market. At its most basic, this is having a simple, expert-looking website with readily accessible, pertinent information about your company. The best you can do is providing them with information about your company, the goods and services you provide, and how to contact you when they need it.

2. Grow your business step-by-step from local to global:

Being online doesn't necessarily entail reaching out to the entire world at once. Growing incrementally by enhancing your internet presence from your local market to a worldwide market makes a lot of sense. Utilizing the proper web tools can help you concentrate your approach to build your business and grab the local market. Create a solid local foundation for yourself so that you can access international markets as a result. Consider local listing websites, directories, B2B portals, and blogs, online networking groups, and forming alliances with other local businesses. These strategies can help your company find prospects and convert them into repeat customer's offline.

3. Use multiple online resources to extend your presence and target on something which really yields you the maximum business:

One of the first things to think about is how to make your company visible to potential customers online. Yes, your website serves as your brand's showcase, but you also need to get your goods and services in front of the people who might use them. You might not have the time or money to handle everything as a small firm, and investing in a useless channel can prove to be a costly oversight. Analyse the identity and web presence resources that can help you achieve the best results possible and direct

your efforts accordingly. MSMEs must exercise caution when allocating funds to the B2B e-marketplace. They must choose the resources that will produce the greatest number of potential clients. For instance, if they are producing industrial items, they can use well-known B2B portals like IndiaMart, Trade India, Alibaba, etc. to find potential customers in both domestic and foreign markets.

4. Nurture your loyal customers – turn them into your marketers:

Finally, consider how you might leverage your most devoted clients to carry out your web promotion. Social media has transformed how individuals share their opinions and experiences with your company. Tired by the continual barrage of marketing messages, we can now just turn to Facebook, Twitter, or LinkedIn for guidance thanks to the internet's abundance of viewpoints. Minutes may make or break a corporation. The widespread use of online social networks has altered how we make purchases. Small or large, businesses of all sizes can benefit from that. Most importantly, these social recommendations are totally free, individualized, and targeted. In conclusion, great influence doesn't necessarily require a big expense when it comes to online marketing. Being consistent, accessible, and relevant online is key. You'll be successful in using the internet to build a clean, professional window display for your offline business if you keep these three points in mind.

5. Major recommendations to policy makers:

With the right initiatives to highlight the significance of internet or digital marketing among the MSMEs, concerned Ministry or Government entities can have a significant impact on the growth of MSMEs. The government has launched numerous initiatives in this direction, including the Government E-marketplace (GeM), a digital platform for government purchases, the MSME Mart, a B2B online marketplace by NSIC, and others. However, taking into account the rate at which digitalization is expanding, particularly in light of the COVID-19 pandemic that broke out in India. Online marketing is sometimes viewed as the only viable company model. Policymakers and organizations that can have a significant impact on the expansion of the MSME sector through consistent activities and policies are given the following recommendations. These suggestions are intended to encourage MSMEs to embrace Internet marketing strategies and to accelerate their growth.

6. Training programs for enhancing awareness:

As the majority of MSMEs are found in numerous studies on the MSME sector to have lower awareness levels regarding the value of being online, Ministry and Concerned Government Bodies must continue to organize training programs in

collaboration with District Industrial Centers or Industry associations to raise awareness of the potential of internet marketing in growing their businesses. Micro and small businesses have been found to have much lower awareness levels. Concerned government entities may significantly affect the success rates of these businesses by raising awareness and encouraging micro and small businesses to adopt internet marketplaces. The manner these companies investigate their business opportunities will change significantly as DIC/industry associations provide more and more advisory support to these companies.

7. Educate MSMEs through best practices and success stories:

According to research studies on the MSME sector, MSMEs' use of Internet marketing tactics to expand their operations is significantly influenced by market or buyer pressure. Therefore, the relevant government agencies or business organizations should provide MSMEs with access to an information portal and reach out to individual MSMEs with case studies of successful MSMEs who have successfully utilized the internet as their business growth strategy and have grown significantly. Case studies, advice on choosing an online marketplace, market prospects particular to a given industry, and data on international markets for businesses looking to expand outside of India should all be included in the site.

8. Schemes for enabling internet marketing adoption:

A specific policy on financial assistance and cost reimbursement for MSMEs' short-term use of online marketing services. To ensure that the services reach a wider portion of the MSME population, this support is required.

Conclusion:

In the current industrial era, Internet marketing plays a significant role in generating economic value for MSMEs' firms. Therefore, it is essential that every small business owner utilize this potent tool as their primary marketing approach in order to expand their enterprise. The government and policy makers must promote this industry in order to transform the current situation among MSMEs in India, where restrictions prevent them from effectively adopting internet marketing as their major marketing technique. Every businessman needs to truly understand that internet marketing is the future doorway to expanding their company. In order for the MSME sector to benefit from the studies' findings and expand their businesses, more and more research is therefore needed in this field.

References:

1. Nallabala Kalyan Kumar and Gugloth Sardar – Asia Pacific Journal and Social Sciences Vol III(1), Jan-Jun 2011, pp128-146
2. Dr. J. Sundararaj – Role of E-Marketing in SMEs International Journal of scientific research and management (IJSRM)||Special Issue On e-Marketing Road Ahead Of India Pages: 191- 196, 2013
3. Upadhyaya, Pallavi and P, Mohanan and Prasad, K Manjunatha (2013) Barriers to adoption of B2B e-marketplaces: an empirical
4. study of Indian manufacturing MSMEs. Review Integrative Business Economics Research, 2 (1). pp. 555-565.
5. Digital Marketing – A Great Opportunity to grow SME Business – Available on <http://innoservsolutions.com/blog/digital-marketing-a-great-opportunity-to-grow-sme-business/>
6. Introduction to E-Marketing – Benefits of E-Marketing - A Small Business Tool Kit – Small Biz Connect: Available On: http://toolkit.smallbiz.nsw.gov.au/part/27/138/64857%ofSMEsusewebsitesasaleschannel:GoogleArticleonTheEconomicTimes-PTIFeb17,2011,04.16pmISTAvailableon:http://articles.economictimes.indiatimes.com/2011-02-17/news/28554965_1_indian-smesinternet-advertising-online-presence
7. 90% of Indian SMEs have no access to Internet: Report - Article on Business Standard - Thursday, September 11, 2014 | 12:14 PM IST Available on: <http://www.businessstandard.com/article/companies/90-of-indian-smes-have-no-access-to-internet-report>
8. Aarzu Khan - July 26, 2013 2:38 PM in Internet, Technology, Zust In / 0 Comments - Available on: <http://www.dazeinfo.com/2013/07/26/opportunity-knocks-95-indian-smes-donhave-web-presence-yet-report/>
9. Glenn Shoosmith – Guardian Professional, Friday 19th October 2-12 10:55BST – Guardian Small Business Network Available On: <http://www.theguardian.com/small-businessnetwork/2012/oct/19/businesses-need-websites>
10. Anupriya Pandey, Varsha Jaiswal – MSME digitalization: Policy initiatives and challenges – Dogo Rangsang Research Journal – Vol-10 Issue-06 No.13 June 2020